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**Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of
Quezon City Residents under Novel Coronavirus 2019
(COVID – 19) Quarantine Protocols**

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic made severe changes in the lifestyle of most Filipino citizens due to different health protocols. The most fascinating impact is the sudden drop of carbon emission, giving a clear sight of the Sierra Madre ranges. This paper seeks to determine and evaluate the measures done by Metro Manila's residents during the implementation of ECQ to point out those which may have done noteworthy influences on the temporary drop in air pollution. Utilizing survey questionnaires, 385 respondents residing in Quezon City were invited to participate in the study to answer a set of questions regarding their demographics, nine general questions, and two sets of a five-point Likert Scale that measures their carbon footprint before and during the quarantine period. The results show that 22.1% of the respondents are unaware of what is carbon footprint; 19.7% do not know that everyday habits affect the environment's carbon footprint, and; 87.5% haven't tried measuring their carbon emissions. Furthermore, 90.9% approved that the pandemic affected the amount of the country's carbon emissions over the past few months. The results also show that the respondents are being responsible for reducing their footprints by generating positive results with only quantitative indexes of VHA (very high adherence) and HA (high adherence). In conclusion, city residents maintain a very high adherence to reducing their carbon footprint.

Keywords: *carbon footprint, COVID-19, Quezon City*

INTRODUCTION

The carbon footprint is the calculation of the overall carbon emissions of a person from everyday activities such as the combustion of fossil fuels for transportation, electricity, etc. These greenhouse gases, expressed as tons of carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalents, can be emitted directly or indirectly (Adanza, 2016). It tests the impact of a person on the environment and climate change in particular. The increase of the world's carbon footprint is an environmental issue to which the Philippines is considered as a relatively small contributor, but is certainly a national concern that must be addressed (Earth Shaker, 2020).

Statistics shown on YCharts (2020) illustrate that from 74.50 million metric tons in 2009, the country recorded an annual 140.10M mt of Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions by December 31, 2019. The clear sight of the Sierra Madre mountain ranges a week after the enhanced community quarantine (ECQ) protocol on March 16, 2020, gave Filipinos living in the National Capital Region (NCR) a glance at what living with better air conditions would look like. Also, due to restricted mobility, curbed road transport, and business shutdowns, there has been a dropped in the concentration of fine particulate matter called PM_{2.5}, a mixture of smoke, soot, dust, chemicals, and other elements, to a third of their normal levels. However, a special report by CREA and Greenpeace Philippines (2020) reveals that the pollution levels in the region are accumulating again as protocols loosen up and urban norms slowly bouncing back.

Inspecting these rudiments that happened during the quarantine state that recent and previous studies on carbon footprint in the Philippines are nondescript, in contrast to developed countries. Thus, a pondering dilemma in lieu of this perceptible situation can be brought out in implying the rate of carbon footprint significantly decreased during the quarantine protocol and how do people in lockdown lessen their amount of carbon emission in the environment.

This paper seeks out in studying to determine and evaluate the measures done by Metro Manila's residents during the implementation of ECQ to point out those which may have done significant influences on the temporary drop in air pollution. This study

provides a discussion on the importance of measuring and mitigating greenhouse gas emission and air pollution especially in a pandemic where everyone is limited on their movement due to the severity in their area as well as reflect on the significant effects of lesser carbon emissions in urbanized areas with high populations. This in turn will allow it to estimate the impact on generated carbon footprint reduction before and after the lockdown by tallying the information given by the respondents alongside determining other factors that affect the given information of the said respondents, allowing it to become a basis for substantial evaluation and can be also a source for other scientific studies that is more oriented on data to infer about the reduction of carbon footprints.

Having the largest area in the National Capital Region, Quezon City is the selected area in conducting the study and will utilize a five-point Likert scale to see the appropriation of the measures done by the chosen respondents. The study limits itself to the response evaluations in terms of the effects of the lockdown with relation to the significant reduction of their carbon footprint. While having the potential to be a shred of counter-evidence for common people's carbon footprint misconceptions, the results can also provide supplementary data for the city's authorities, while influencing people the importance of mitigating air pollution even after the current pandemic.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Definition and Origin of Carbon Footprint

Carbon footprint is the total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions caused directly and indirectly by an individual, organization, event or product. It is determined by summing up the emissions from each point of the lifespan of a product or service (material production, manufacturing, use, and end-of-life). The GHG's whose sum results in a carbon footprint can come from the production and consumption of fossil fuels, food, manufactured goods, materials, roads or transportation. And despite its importance, carbon footprints are difficult to calculate exactly due to poor knowledge and short data regarding the complex interactions between contributing processes – including the influence of natural processes that store or release carbon dioxide.

The development of the term carbon footprint was the reverse of ecological footprint, which originated in the scientific literature and then extended to general usage. Carbon footprint first gained currency in the popular media, in the early 2000s, and it took several years for the term to become well established in academic usage. A search of the vast ScienceDirect journal database shows that it was not until 2008 that “carbon footprint” began appearing regularly in the title of scientific papers, though now of course it can be found hundreds of times. Today, some experts propose the use of the term climate footprint, because it encompasses the full range of gases that can be involved with anthropogenic effects on climate, including ones that are not carbon-based.

Definition and Causes of Carbon Footprint Emissions

There are both natural and human sources of carbon dioxide emissions. Natural sources include decomposition, ocean release and respiration. Human sources come from activities like cement production, deforestation as well as the burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and natural gas. Due to human activities, the atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide has been rising extensively since the Industrial Revolution and has now reached dangerous levels not seen in the last 3 million years. Human sources of carbon dioxide emissions are much smaller than natural emissions but they have upset the natural balance that existed for many thousands of years before the influence of humans. This is because natural sinks remove around the same quantity of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere than are produced by natural sources. This had kept carbon dioxide levels balanced and in a safe range. But human sources of emissions have upset the natural balance by adding extra carbon dioxide to the atmosphere without removing any.

Since the Industrial Revolution, human sources of carbon dioxide emissions have been growing. Human activities such as the burning of oil, coal and gas, as well as deforestation are the primary cause of the increased carbon dioxide concentrations in the atmosphere. There are 87% of all human-produced carbon dioxide emissions come from the burning of fossil fuels like coal, natural gas and oil. The remainder results from the

clearing of forests and other land use changes (9%), as well as some industrial processes such as cement manufacturing (4%).

Apart from being created by human activities, carbon dioxide is also released into the atmosphere by natural processes. The Earth's oceans, soil, plants, animals and volcanoes are all-natural sources of carbon dioxide emissions. Human sources of carbon dioxide are much smaller than natural emissions but they upset the balance in the carbon cycle that existed before the Industrial Revolution. The amount of carbon dioxide produced by natural sources is completely offset by natural carbon sinks and has been for thousands of years. Before the influence of humans, carbon dioxide levels were quite steady because of this natural balance. There are 42.84% of all naturally produced carbon dioxide emissions come from ocean-atmosphere exchange. Other important natural sources include plant and animal respiration (28.56%) as well as soil respiration and decomposition (28.56%). A minor amount is also created by volcanic eruptions (0.03%).

Direct and Indirect Carbon Footprint Emissions

The concept of emission scopes was introduced by The Greenhouse Gas Protocol (GHG Protocol). Its goal is to define how a company controls the emissions it is responsible for. The GHG Protocol is the most widely used international accounting tool for government and business leaders to understand, quantify and measure greenhouse gas emissions (GHG).

Direct Greenhouse Gas Emissions come from sources that are owned or controlled by the reporting entity. This could be the emissions that are directly created by manufacturing goods, for example, factory fumes. This does not account for the combustion of biomass.

Indirect Emissions from Energy are emissions physically occur at the facility where electricity, steam and cooling or heating are generated. But as a user of the energy, the consuming party is still responsible for the Greenhouse Gas Emissions that are being created.

Indirect Emission are emissions from sources that are not owned and not directly controlled by the reporting company. However, they are related to the company's activities. This is usually considered to be the supply chain of the company, so emissions caused by vendors within the supply chain, outsourced activities, and employee travel and commute. In many industries, this emissions account for the biggest amount of GHG emissions. This is due to the fact that in today's economy, many tasks are outsourced, and few companies own the entire value chain of their products.

Organic Sector

A recent study by the Rodale Institute found that, if all conventional agricultural land started using organic farming practices, such as mulch tilling and seasonal crop rotations, agriculture could – in theory – capture 100% of annual carbon emissions. The study also found that organic farms have lower greenhouse emissions than conventional farms due to avoidance of synthetic fertilizers, which are compounded with nitrogen and require fossil fuels to produce. However, some studies have argued that it conclusion is premature as lower emissions depend on the amount fertilizers used on organic and conventional farms and the amount of food that can be produced per acre of land.

A previous study reported that the concept of organic farming and sufficiency economy can help to reduce GHG emissions from agricultural activities and improve soil fertility and the soil carbon stock (Chaimanuskul et al., 2011; Kaufman et al., 2011; Thailand Research Fund, 2010). The latter study also reported the CF of organic and conventional farming and showed that organic farming had a lower CF than conventional farming.

Processed Products Sector

Food processing (converting produce from the farm into final products), transport, packaging and retail all require energy and resource inputs. Many assume that eating local is key to a low-carbon diet, however, transport emissions are often a very small

percentage of food's total emissions – only 6% globally. Whilst supply chain emissions may seem high, at 18%, it's essential for reducing emissions by preventing food waste. Food waste emissions are large: one-quarter of emissions (3.3 billion tonnes of CO₂eq) from food production ends up as wastage either from supply chain losses or consumers. Durable packaging, refrigeration and food processing can all help to prevent food waste.

Reducing emissions from food production will be one of our greatest challenges in the coming decades. Unlike many aspects of energy production where viable opportunities for upscaling low-carbon energy – renewable or nuclear energy – are available, the ways in which we can decarbonize agriculture are less clear. We need inputs such as fertilizers to meet growing food demands, and we can't stop cattle from producing methane. We will need a menu of solutions: changes to diets; food waste reduction; improvements in agricultural efficiency; and technologies that make low-carbon food alternatives scalable and affordable.

Energy and Transport Sector

In a report published by Transport and Traffic Planners Inc. (TTPI) in collaboration with CPI Energy Philippines Inc. in 2010, the authors reviewed and estimated the number of emissions in various developments in the transport and power sectors and identified interventions on reducing carbon emissions for the development a holistic approach for assessing cost-effectiveness. The focal points of the report are being concerned with the transport and power sector and the released tables and graphs provides a detailed viewpoint of what the authorities must do in reducing carbon emissions in the country, specifically in the sectors mentioned in the report. The summary of these solutions for the sectors can be described as the necessary changes that the Philippines need in order to organize the energy distribution of the energy and transport sector.

Related to this, Balanay and Lungu in their paper studied the exposure of local jeepney drivers in the Philippines to selected VOC's, which is then compared to other studies which produce more large-scale data on the amount of these compounds on known cities for selected countries. The study limits itself to other factors that might affect

the drivers from their exposures such as their communal habits during pastime but it provides a conclusion that the exposures may differ from one driver to another due to their itineraries and the said limitations on their leisure hours.

Reduction of Industrial Carbon Footprints

About one-fifth of U.S. greenhouse gas emissions come directly from industrial sources, such as manufacturing, food processing, mining, and construction. These direct emissions result from diverse processes, including the on-site combustion of fossil fuels for heat and power, non-energy use of fossil fuels, and chemical processes used in iron, steel, and cement production.

In addition, industry generates indirect emissions from the centrally generated electricity it consumes. The industrial sector makes up about one quarter of total U.S. electricity sales. If direct and indirect emissions are combined, the industrial sector is the largest emitting sector in the U.S. economy, responsible for 29.3 percent of total emissions.

There are many ways to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the industrial sector, including energy efficiency, fuel switching, combined heat and power, use of renewable energy, and the more efficient use and recycling of materials. Many industrial processes have no existing low-emission alternative and will require carbon capture and storage to reduce emissions over the long term.

Average Carbon Footprints and Definition and Methods of Carbon Offsetting

A review from Weidema et. al. on carbon footprint indicators stated that the indicators on carbon dioxide footprints are not that enough and the authors also raised the question that if there is a need for an ISO standard to such a relevant scaling system. With set-ups on carbon footprint indicators not being in-sync with each other, the authors

ended their article that creating a fixed system on indicators is now on demand for the benefit of the consumers and the companies that manufacture products.

Wiedmann and Barrett's paper on reviewing another footprint measure that is bigger than carbon footprint, which is the ecological footprint, also has the same remark over the fact that footprints in particular, are increasingly becoming more relevant in a world where consumer knowledge and product transparency is a norm. Comparison between the ecological footprint to biodiversity footprint is explored by Hanafiah et. al. in 2012 with the results being that some factors, specifically the utilization of land area, is different to the emissions of carbon dioxide, which is a derivative form the much larger ecological footprint.

Alongside with that, Galli et. al. in 2010 reinforces the statements that different footprint indicators are included into the same family where they belong and affect each other in the process. A 2013 study by Fang et. al. also supports the statements brought up by the former, as over the past two decades, footprint-style indicators became a thing and because of this, a much more complex of understanding must be set upon these indicators and categorize them as a family.

Current methods for estimation of carbon footprints in the atmosphere is given by Agrawal et. al. in their study in 2011 which states the numerous techniques for assessing the carbon footprints of countries. It also encapsulates the concepts of factors affecting the carbon footprint of a country, especially the gross domestic product per capita and the living conditions in the said areas. It also presents data on which volatile organic compounds (VOC's) are commonly scattered in the atmosphere of some countries. However, the authors also stated that by the time of their study there is no defined standard for the compounds measured to determine the carbon footprint, but all institutions comply to the same protocols for measuring these emissions in the atmosphere.

In a 2016 study by Mancini et. al., the most influential among the methodology of the ecological footprint indicators is the carbon footprint, where the most common

indicative of the footprint is through the Average Forest Carbon Sequestration (AFCS) calculations. The paper explores the many versions of calculations, which ended up in the researchers of the said study to have comparable differences in the formerly used indicative values to the new ones being used.

Kyoto Protocol and Market Mechanisms (Mandatory and Voluntary)

The study of Babiker et. al. on the Kyoto protocol and the developing countries like the Philippines presented information on how developed countries would implement certain obligations to the world by directly helping said developing countries and lessening their carbon footprints. This includes changes in trade policies, compensations for damages, and concessions for special tariffs. As such actions are made, it will create a ripple effect upon the world trade and onto said developing countries, which is not a big deal. In this paper, it is stated that upon releasing control policies on the trading game means that there will be a positive side of reducing carbon footprints and a negative side where most companies that are on the fuel and energy sector, are heavily affected by the decisions made by such a protocol.

Lasco and Pulihin's study in 2003 pinpoints the focus of Philippine Forest Ecosystems for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG's) in the Philippines. They resolved that in this study, the opportunities for reforestation efforts are indispensable for the reduction of such emissions but such matters have to be addressed before it is totally in to the progressive goals of the United Nations.

On one side, the United States has dropped its agreement on the said protocol back when President George Bush was the president. In the study of Böhringer and Löschel in 2003, the said withdrawal of the US has noteworthy consequences on effectiveness, compliance costs, and excess costs of market power under the protocol.

United Nations' Action Plan on Sustainable Development Goals

The United Nations' 2019 sustainable development report translates that most of the sustainable development goals were still not met or not in the right track, while the status of some goals is still unclear. Despite this, there is still progress on the way until the pandemic came into the mix. In line with the 2019 report, another publication from the UN released the distinct trends from the many reports and publications in the field of science and technology. In the conclusion of the report, a call for action was mentioned to the following, like strengthening human well-being and capabilities, the shift of sustainable and just economies, building food systems and healthy nutrition patterns, universal access to decarbonized energy, and the promotion of sustainable development in both communities and in the field of academe.

By comparison to the previous year, the sustainable development report released by the United Nations in the United States for 2020 reveal that the sustainable development goals on the year are in bad shape due to the short-term impacts that was brought by the sudden global pandemic brought by COVID-19. In particular, SDG's 3 (Good Health and Well - Being) and 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) were highly affected because of the pandemic. This in turn also affected the other goals that were closely linked to the two goals that were directly pinned down by the pandemic. The 2019 and 2020 reports are also a major concern on a report from the UN Secretary General.

Local and International Action Plans on Carbon Emissions

Three reports from Asian Development Bank *also detail* the effects of carbon footprints in various *contexts*, with it *has been studying* the effects of road constructions in India (ADB, 2010), foreseeing options analysis and forecasts on carbon emissions (ADB, 2009), and the pathways for low-carbon development in the Philippines (ADB, 2017). The methodologies for the said reports projected the number of releases of carbon dioxide in the aforementioned countries where the reports originate from and gives a conclusion on the future goals for sustainability for reducing emissions on these countries.

On the other hand, the World Wide Fund (WWF) feature report on ecological footprints and improving local capital in the Pacific region shows that the business in the Pacific must be improved to find solutions that is distinctly suited for the needs of the local people while keeping the amount of carbon footprints at bay as a way to move things forward in the said region. Meanwhile, existing reports of greenhouse gas inventories and fuel economies in the United States reveals the different consumptions of different industrial models used mostly in automobiles and factories and giving the conclusion of what companies could do to lessen the impact of their products.

In the report "Innovations for Sustainability: Pathways to an efficient and sufficient post-pandemic future" that was published by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), it has expounded that the tension between the achievements in transformative governance since the adoption of the 2030 Agenda and the current global political trends made it more difficult for the implementation of sustainability plans and projects that related to projects like the implementations of development projects. Many states have introduced frameworks which goal is to accentuate coordination across policy sectors, levels of state, multi-stakeholder engagement and high-level political leadership. In line with this, solutions that are related to nature are also a trend. Although the pandemic has accelerated negativities such as global autocratization and polarization of societies, it has also provided opportunities for sufficiency and innovation policies, which in turn has made the scientific community to be proactive in the role of the government especially during this time and after the pandemic ends.

Personal Methods to Reduce Carbon Footprints

In a paper by Pinkert and Sticker, they delivered arguments on whether the quantity of offsprings of the parents must be counted as a part of their count in their total carbon emanations. They explained on why some principles on totaling the amount of carbon footprint is problematic in the contribution of an individual's own footprint. Therefore, encapsulating the point that gauging the difference of carbon impact activity makes to overall emissions while personal carbon footprint procedures how much is the accomplished number of emissions of the individual.

Severo et. al's paper on measuring the impact of the pandemic on three factors, environmental awareness, sustainable consumption, and social responsibility has been proven that people in Brazil and Portugal have positively adapted to the impacts of the said factors during the pandemic. however, the said factors are also moderated during the course of the pandemic. Which resulted in the researchers noting that the current pandemic is affected by social, environmental, and economic influences.

Overview of COVID-19 Origins

On December 31, 2019, the China Health Authority alerted the World Health Organization (WHO) to several cases of pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan City in Hubei Province in central China. The cases had been reported since December 8, 2019, and many patients worked at or lived around the local Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market although other early cases had no exposure to this market (Lu et. al., 2020).

Sheheen et. al.'s review on the current pandemic on the earlier months states that the coronavirus disease 19 (COVID-19) is a highly transmittable and pathogenic viral infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which emerged in Wuhan, China and sustained to proliferate on the various areas of the world. As the virus is similar to the family of formerly acknowledged SARS-COV pathogens, previously used animal models are utilized to study the pathogenicity of the new virus. Similar virus variants have also been assessed in hopes to find a treatment to those who were afflicted by the disease. The only available therapeutical treatments during that time are Remdesivir, Lopinavir, Rltonavir, and Oseltamivir which has a substantial result of momentarily delaying the infection of the virus to those who were infected.

Clinical manifestations of COVID-19 are diverse, mimicking those of pneumonia and commonly presenting with fever, cough, myalgias, fatigue, and less commonly with diarrhea and vomiting. The pneumonia progressively develops into severe acute respiratory infection, acute respiratory distress syndrome, acute respiratory failure, hepatic injury, kidney failure and cardiovascular complications. (Naji, 2020).

Harapan et. al.'s literature review on the current pandemic captivantly said that due to rapid transmission, countries of the world must increase attention into surveillance of probable people who are infected by the disease and to scale up the readiness and response operations as a measure to mitigate the spread of the virus.

Cruz and Zeichner also expressed that the knowledge on how COVID-19 works, like on younger people where there is still much more to dig upon when it comes to the impact of this virus on children as well as the impact of children on viral spread. Rothan and Byrareddy also adds up to the former by declaring that the practice of widespread procedures to diminish person-to-person transmission of COVID-19 are compulsory to regulate the current outbreak along with distinct attention and exertions to protect or reduce transmission in vulnerable populations. The said disease too is also moderately understood due to its intricacies in inflammatory characteristics as distinguished by McElvaney et. al.

However, on the final months of the year 2020, the European Centre for Disease and Prevention and Control (ECDC) stated that an increase in the spread of a new mutated variant that was first exposed in the United Kingdom has far worse severities in the transmission of COVID-19.

On an article published by the magazine Science, the UK Variant of COVID-19 is placed under a higher level of concern, as this article states that the new variant of the virus has seemingly developed 17 genetic alterations that lead to amino acid fluctuations in its proteins all at once, a feat never seen before in the coronavirus. This is distressing since experts cannot cope up on how the variants of the virus yield faster and mutate under a short span of time. Another article from the said magazine tells that while the virus now has a vaccine to combat the spread of it, there is a doubt on the scientific community whether the made vaccines can cause life-threatening reactions such as anaphylaxis.

Local and International Effect of COVID-19

Haleem and Javaid's statement on the effects of COVID-19 on the daily lives of people is categorized into the healthcare, economic, and social postulates. Because of this, the pandemic caused a heavy toll on the supply of the global economy and now causes a great ripple effect upon the world economy for the following years.

Boissay and Rungcharoenkitkul in their study assessed the macroeconomic effects of the COVID-19 pandemic where they noted that unlike the past pandemics, the world faced a synchronized lockdown to prevent the spread of the disease. Typically, this led into the world falling into an economic trauma where the unprecedented economic sudden stop would need to be looked upon in order to see what would happen to the world economy. In conclusion, the researchers in this study stated that the course of action is fixed and ready-to-go yet the damages right now are still unprecedented. Other than that, the proper decisions between the pandemic and the economy must be needed on this day and age.

In addition to this, Caggiano et. al. studied that the uncertainties of the current pandemic will bring a considerable amount of economic damage that is brought by the deterioration of financial conditions that is predicted to be in place for a year. However, they concluded that these damages would be much more likely a conservative amount rather than a full-scale economic depression.

A study made by Barman et. al. denotes that the impact of COVID-19 in the food supply chain made it harder for those in the food area have numerous difficulties ahead such as guaranteeing food handling, distinguishing the virus in conditions where food is made and reached out to the consumers, and maintaining proper working conditions while being safe amidst the threat of the virus. The food sector must be wary that a need for a lean comeback is needed for the full recovery of the sector.

Rowan and Galanakis in their review paper stressed out that multi-actor innovation hubs that will support, connect, and enable businesses to recover and pivot beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. They have conjectured that climate action, digitization, manufacturing, and sustainable food production, security, and waste mitigation as

possible candidates for boosting the economy back. In their paper, they also recommend community transitioning, training, enterprise, and employment to low carbon economies as key areas to outsource manpower for the improvement of economies of nations post-pandemic.

The work of Engle et. al. on the mobility effects of COVID-19 used the data available on the Global Positioning System (GPS) datasets to see the changes of the average distance traveled by the people of the United States during the quarantine measures that was implemented due to the pandemic. After using these datasets to see a correlation, the results turned that with the prevalence of COVID-19, the population mobility reacts strongly to vicissitudes in the announcements and the cases of the COVID-19 in the areas where individuals live.

Papagiannidis et. al.'s opinion paper on sharing the insights of IT professionals on how do they adapt to the current pandemic. On this paper it was shown that businesses and the IT industry must have to work in synchronization with each other to be resilient in the threat of a sudden pandemic such as COVID-19.

In a paper released by Gu and Wang on assessing the agricultural cooperatives in Shanghai, China, they have found out that the vegetable market has been heavily affected especially on the sales negotiations. where it affected the gap between the field prices and the prices sold at markets. They also noticed that the income of farmers has been declining as the pandemic goes on and that by stabilizing the market means to secure the agricultural insurance of the farmers.

Pascual et. al. explores the standpoints of clinical sexologists about the impact of COVID-19 on their patients' sexual health, as well as the professional challenges they have faced during the present pandemic. The outcomes of their study concluded up in revealing that remarkable interconnected issues are getting bad due to the dilemma caused by COVID-19.

On a study that was published by Mok et. al., they relayed that most of the students in mainland China would want to have overseas studies plans against the impending threat of the COVID-19 pandemic. In their study where they have 2739 respondents, 84%

of them stated that they showed no interest in studying in other countries, while the one who would want to study in other countries, specifically the United States, Hong Kong, United Kingdom, Japan, and Taiwan. This showed an effect that because of the pandemic, a lot of students would want to remain in their homeland for a while the pandemic goes on, which in turn hinders a lot of possibilities for the mobility of international students. The effects of the pandemic in academic institutions is also detailed by teachers such as an article published by Bush and Bentley in their narratives on the pandemic and how do they innovate and cope. The same can be also said with a paper published by Uhi which focuses on his institution's subsidiarity to students and how does the school innovate in the "online learning" mode.

Jiang and Wen's study on the management and marketing of hotel businesses on reviewing a lot of literature and hotel management trends revealed that a proposed trend to make hotels profitable again is the use of artificial intelligence (AI) into their services, while also utilizing the hotel not only for leisure and relaxation but also for entertainment purposes. These insights will also help the hotel managements to carry on even amidst the pandemic. In relation to this, Shin and Kang published a paper to examine the impact of expected interaction and cleanliness on perceived health risk and hotel booking intentions of hotel customers. In their study they have noted that the theoretical implication of this is identifying the decision-making process of the customers, with the practical implications of this is to improve the methodologies of hotel services in the tourism sector.

Performances in companies and their coping strategy were given light in Nguyen et. al.'s paper where they utilized a survey to look upon 672 companies in Vietnam and then formulating a logistic regression model to see the gist on the companies' strategic choices on coping with the pandemic that was based on their degree of their factors of their profiles, entrepreneurial factors, financial distress and the interactions between the said companies. In their study they concluded that a lot of these companies turned into cost-cutting strategies in order to thrive amidst the pandemic while also noticing that interactions in the companies might suggest that potential growth and partnerships can

happen even during the pandemic as well as noting that managements tend to stress more on the global risks of the pandemic rather than localized risks.

Lee and Trimi in their paper explored that sustainable innovations is a must in order for the economy to thrive even in the pandemic. In their paper, they explored the frameworks of convergence innovation and discussed on how will it be effective in proliferating sustainable innovations while most of the people in sequestered in their households with their mobility is very limited.

Yet, innovations amidst the pandemic can happen, as it was detailed by one innovative article given by DIn et. al. on the production of protective equipment for frontliners that are combatting against the COVID-19 pandemic, that was facing a decline in supplies due to the lack of availability of the said protective equipment. The authors discussed that the pandemic opened a new opportunity in the field of computer aided 3D design. They stressed out that innovation might be made easier and faster if the utilization of CAD were to be taught as part of the standard Science, Engineering, Medical and Dental curriculum. They stated that the realization of collaborative efforts of the dental and medical profession with the academic and industry sectors can still be strengthened.

The idea for such innovations was also supported by a paper that was published by Brem et. al. where they explored technologies that may improve the lives of the people during the pandemic. In the paper, they scrutinized on how 3D Printing, flexible manufacturing systems, big data analytics, and smart healthcare watchables on devices like smartphones can be effective for potential innovation during the time where a world is stricken by a pandemic.

In an editorial article that was written by Škorić et. al., they noted about the impact of the whopping number of articles have made professionals and the general public about the importance of scientific research and its implications during the COVID-19 pandemic. It also has shown the benefits of open access knowledge to the people but they have emphasized that well designed papers and peer reviewed methodologies is a must, which is very crucial to take notes of as other journals published in the time of the pandemic is still unsatisfactory, which can prove fatal if decisions are mostly based on impulsive desires.

Comparison on Previous Background Studies before the COVID-19 Pandemic

Adanza's report in 2016 tackled the barriers of non-adherence to acknowledged procedures to reduce carbon emissions in the environment. As its emphasis is mostly on an academy vicinity in an urban setting, the reflections of his study are noteworthy as it gives the extent of barriers to observance to said methodologies. Although it limits itself to the author's academic institution, the conclusions of the study are significant as it gives a conceptualization on the extent of such barriers by giving data to back it up. The author's recommendations on the paper are also on point with the situation in the Philippines during that time, and still can be reflected upon today.

Assessments of Researchers on Carbon Footprints during the Pandemic

In Cranston's work published in 2010, he deliberated the causations of the accumulation of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere in modern day scenarios and possible scenarios in the future. In addition, his paper determined correlating equations for the carbon and ecological footprint as well as finding that the main driving forces behind these emissions are the yielding growths of the economy in the countries around the world. The recent studies of Gan et. al. and Rugani and Caro this year also provides supplementary background on the possible scenarios predicted out by Cranston in his study, with the exception of the ongoing pandemic.

Griffith et. al.'s current work on the assessing the air pollution transports during the first week of the pandemic using Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPPLIT) data model and Community Multiscale Air Quality (CMAQ) v5.2.1 data model highlighted that the number of pollutants in the air that goes to neighboring countries such as Taiwan had lessened a significant amount of air pollution in China's atmosphere. Another case study from Nižetic revealed that the sector of air transport was affected heavily in the European region, while the cargo and logistics were boosted due to the need of medical supplies to fight against the global pandemic.

Wang et. al.'s work on assessing the changes in air quality in China showed that during the COVID-19 lockdown, the quality of the air in China has significantly improved in the urban areas in the mainland territories. The study shows the air quality index and the presence of some major air pollutants. Scatterplot graphs of the air quality indexes (AQI's) are shown in this paper and it was compared to previous years.

However, in a journal pre-proof essay delivered by Riccò et. al., they stressed out that the correlations of the emissions of the number of air pollutants in modern industrialized such as mainland China and Italy should not be concluded mostly due to the looming threat of the affected people of the pandemic, as the incidence rate is considered to be far different from the incidence rate of the said virus, and that the lessening of these pollutants must be piloted before the spread of the pandemic to other areas. In their conclusion, they said that further solutions must be delivered in order to know the ratio of the pandemic's status to the number of pollutants in the atmosphere of modern countries.

The paper released by Kroll et. al. on the chemical effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the air quality of the world stated that most scientific studies have rushed to the fact that the air quality had become cleaner due to the lockdown measures to prevent the pandemic. However, much more must be put into the equation and looking upon the primary and secondary pollutants means that the quality of air in the environment may not be as good as many thought it is, but for the next years after the pandemic, the quality might be worse for the number of pollutants that are present in the atmosphere. With the complex realm of atmospheric chemistry, the researchers also stated that most of the air qualities around the world would be different due to the policies and the strengths of the implementations that was governed to update on the quality of air of a country.

Zhou et. al. in their paper listed companies in the Chinese Stock Market using ARIMA intervention analysis that was utilized to produce a system dynamic model to analyze what will be formed in examining the impact of the pandemic. They stated that waste management programs and zero waste management efforts in China may have to face uncanny challenges in the near future, where they also recommend that simulating the impacts of such movements must be considered.

Contextualizing the pandemic is given by a published paper from Sovacool et. al. which explores the many stories of the well-documented pandemic. In their paper, they illustrated that humanity created a multi-scalar and multilayered nature of societal rejoinders to the pandemic in which it demonstrated on people being educated to adapt a series of changes, while also bolstering the capabilities of infrastructures and institutions to monitor, manage, and combat the spread of the current pandemic. In turn, this allows the harnessing of innovations in the scientific community while rapidly developing new efforts to fight back the ravaging threat. It also utilized methodologies to jumpstart the economies of nations back with strategies that are backed upon by scientific studies while having to protect those who are vulnerable to the disease. However, the researchers also stressed on their paper that the pandemic posed a scenario of societal mobilization that can also happen on the looming threat of climate change that can damage the world far worse than the current pandemic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The design's method of this certain study is quantitative; as it provides more focal points for the ability to come up with a comprehensive statistical analysis (Mersdorf, 2016). A survey research design was employed in this study to establish a foundation in determining and evaluating the actions done by Metro Manila's inhabitants, specifically those living in Quezon City during the enactment of quarantine health protocols to identify those which may have done substantial influences to the temporary drop in air pollution. To define it, survey research design is an extensive cross-sectional approach, where a number of cases are considered at a particular time and the data is gathered to study the opinions, behavior, attitudes, habits, desires, values and beliefs etc. (Farooq, 2015).

Research Instrument

The research instrument that was used by the researchers are the survey questionnaires prepared to gauge the different activities done by Metro Manila's inhabitants, particularly Quezon City residents, which we chose as our chosen respondents for the course of the study. The researchers will look upon the said actions in stark correlations throughout the course of the quarantine health protocols to identify those which may have done substantial influences to the temporary drop in air pollution. As said by Mersdorf in 2016, the utilization of surveys and questionnaires is one of the frequently used practices in quantitative research.

Determining the Sample Size

The chosen population are the inhabitants of Quezon City in studying to determine and evaluate the measures done by the residents during ECQ to obtain data which may have done significant influences to the noteworthy decline of air pollution throughout the said period. The researchers will be executing a sampling technique that was adapted from an experience management sample size calculator of the website, Qualtrics.com, to the selected respondents in order to cut down time and resource limitations. For this study, the researchers would use said sampling size calculator for obtaining the sample size. This is for the reason that (1) the population of the selected respondents is manageable enough to the current study and (2) for the ease of the sampling for the chosen respondents.

The researchers then distributed their survey instrument to people who live in Quezon City via Facebook and Facebook Messenger, which redirects them to the Google Forms link in the message. The respondents for the study are available to all ages, thus having the advantage to be easily accessible even amidst the pandemic and to the respondents also. The respondents were voluntary and has been reminded of the verification of the data collected prior to the regulatory collection of data as stated in the Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

By utilizing the experience management sample size calculator formula of the website, Qualtrics.com, the researchers can determine how much respondents are needed to produce a significant number of responses that can provide the data for the objectives of the study.

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Feedback

Determining sample size: how to make sure you get the correct sample size

6 min read

How many is enough? Over the years, researchers have grappled with the problem of finding the perfect sample size for statistically sound results. Here we shed light on some methods and tools for sample size determination.

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Feedback

- + **If your sample is too small**, you may include a disproportionate number of individuals which are outliers and anomalies. These skew the results and you don't get a fair picture of the whole population.
- + **If the sample is too big**, the whole study becomes complex, expensive and time-consuming to run, and although the results are more accurate, the benefits don't outweigh the costs.

If you've already worked out your variables you can get to the right sample size quickly with the online sample size calculator below:

Sample size calculator

Confidence Level:

Population Size:

Margin of Error:

Ideal Sample Size:

If you want to start from scratch in determining the right sample size for your market research, let us walk you through the steps.

Figures 3.1 – 3.2 (preceding page): The website of Qualtrics, where the researchers utilized the sampling size calculator to determine the number of participants to be used for the study.

Noting n as the sample size, the sample size calculator will arrive at the formula, which is:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot s \cdot (1 - s)}{e^2}$$

With Z being the Z-score, s being the standard deviation, and e being the margin of error for the sample size.

As the population of Quezon City is still tallied in the recent census of the Philippine Statistics Authority. The researchers resorted to the prediction of the population that was given in the websites of World Population Review and Population.City which noted that if the population rate of the city would be like the same from 2010 - 2015, the population for the year 2021 would be about 3,160,000. As this is a very large number, the researchers inserted it into the sample size calculator of Qualtrics.com and apportioned with a confidence level of 95% (with Z-score = 1.96), a margin of error of $\pm 5\%$, and a secured standard deviation of 0.5, the researchers took the place of it in order to determine the sample size that is to be utilized by the study.

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot (0.5) \cdot (1 - 0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \cdot 0.25}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 384.16$$

As the n in this equation is **384.16**, the researchers would take **385** respondents who will participate in the prepared online survey.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers will use questionnaires as their research instrument, which will be done using Google Forms. Google Forms is a free survey tool that is a part of the Google Suite, commonly known as Google Docs, which is Google's very own office suite that can collect information from people via personalized quizzes or surveys (Gavin, 2019). The online survey that the researchers did is then separated by four parts. The first part is the collection of the demographic profiles of the respondents, which comprises of the following:

Demographics:

- 1. E – Mail Address**
- 2. Full Name**
- 3. Age**
- 4. Gender**
- 5. Complete Address**
- 6. Contact Number**
- 7. Living Status**
- 8. Marital Status**
- 9. Education Status**
- 10. Employment Status**

The second part contains nine questions that will let the researchers attain the responses that will answer general concepts for the purpose of the given study, which

involves if they are aware of what is carbon footprint, what have they done for in response to it, and have they ever done something as a measure to counter it. These general concepts are then placed into the following questions:

Survey Questions:

- 1. Are you familiar with the phrase "carbon footprint"?***
- 2. Are you aware that our everyday habits have a huge effect on adding to the environment's carbon footprint?***
- 3. Have you ever tried measuring your overall carbon emissions before?***
- 4. Do you agree that the effects of carbon footprint will eventually disappear?***
- 5. Do you think that the lockdown caused by COVID-19 affected our country's total carbon emission these past few months?***
- 6. Can you recall one thing you did that you think helped reduce your carbon footprint BEFORE the pandemic started?***
- 7. Can you recall one thing you did that you think helped reduce your carbon footprint DURING the pandemic?***
- 8. Can you recall one thing you did in order to help reduce the carbon footprint of OTHERS BEFORE the pandemic?***
- 9. Can you recall one thing you planned to do to help reduce your carbon footprint even during the pandemic?***

The third part is a set of scenarios on a five-point Likert Scale Test. A Likert Scale Test is a scale used to measure the attitude wherein the respondents are asked to indicate the level of agreement or disagreement with the statements related to the stimulus objects (Businessjargons.com, 2016). The said test presents a set of actions that

feature a scenario that will let the respondents to select their responses based on their experiences before the incidence of quarantine measures brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. This is patterned to a five-point Likert Scale Test that was from a study from a study made by Adanza in 2016 entitled, "Barriers to Mitigate Carbon Footprint in a Selected Academic Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines". The researchers only adapted the part of the Likert-scale type inquiries on the degree of adherence to the measures that restrain carbon footprint emissions and barriers to the said observances.

The fourth part is similar to the third part; however, it focuses on the same assemblage of scenarios that will let the respondents to choose their responses constructed on their understandings and involvements during the implementation of quarantine measures brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. The given circumstances of the Likert Scale Test on the third and fourth parts are the following:

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint:

- 1. I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.***
- 2. I change incandescent lamp to fluorescent to save more energy.***
- 3. I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.***
- 4. I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.***
- 5. I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.***
- 6. I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.***
- 7. I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.***
- 8. I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.***
- 9. I avoid purchasing useless products.***
- 10. I support forestation/Earth Hour.***
- 11. I recycle papers and other scraps.***

12. I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.

13. I do not throw trash anywhere.

14. I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.

15. When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.

16. I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty, staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.

For formality, the conducted online survey has a disclaimer that the participant who will join in the online survey are reminded of the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, in which the researchers state that only those involved in the current study will have access to their given information and the exchange of which will be facilitated through email or hard copy. The collected data from the participants will be kept in spreadsheet format under the secured storage of Google Suite and the local computer drives of the researchers. As this study accumulates sensitive data, they will only be used as crucial information for the undergoing research study. The online survey in Google Forms opened at January 14, 2021, 12 NN. It lasted for about a week and two days, where it was closed on 12 NN, January 23, 2021.

The survey questions used can be seen at Appendix B – Survey Form and the researcher's social media posts on a formal invitation to the survey can be seen at Appendix D — Invitation to the Online Survey.

Statistical Analysis

The demographics for the ages will be categorized under a horizontal bar graph as the age range is spread out. On the other hand, gender, living status, marital status, education status, and employment status would be represented in pie graphs.

For the third and fourth part which introduces a set of scenarios on a five-point Likert Scale Test before and during the quarantine measures started, the researchers will represent the five choices on the with numbers; "strongly agree" will be denoted as 5, "agree" will be denoted as 4, "undecided" will be denoted as 3, "disagree" will be denoted as 2, and "strongly disagree" will be denoted as 1. The numbers would be then tallied in each question to get the mean with the standard error of $\pm 5\%$.

Table 3.1: Extent of Level of Adherence taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint (Before the Quarantine Measures brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic)

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint (Before the Pandemic)	Mean (Margin of Error = $\pm 5\%$)	Quantitative Index (QI)
Scenario #1: I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.		
Scenario #2: I change incandescent lamp or fluorescent to save more energy.		
Scenario #3: I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.		
Scenario #4: I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.		
Scenario #5: I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.		
Scenario #6: I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.		
Scenario #7: I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.		
Scenario #8: I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.		
Scenario #9: I avoid purchasing useless products.		

Scenario #10: I support forestation/Earth Hour.		
Scenario #11: I recycle papers and other scraps.		
Scenario #12: I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.		
Scenario #13: I do not throw trash anywhere.		
Scenario #14: I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.		
Scenario #15: When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.		
Scenario #16: I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty, staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.		

Legend:

4.20-5.00 – very high adherence (VHA)

2.60-3.39- moderate adherence (MA)

1.00-1.79- no adherence (NA)

3.40-4.19- high adherence (HA)

1.80-2.59- low adherence (LA)

Table 3.2: Extent of Level of Adherence taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint
(During the Quarantine Measures brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic)

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint (During the Pandemic)	Mean (Margin of Error = ±5%)	Quantitative Index (QI)
Scenario #1: I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.		
Scenario #2: I change incandescent lamp or fluorescent to save more energy.		

Scenario #3: I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.		
Scenario #4: I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.		
Scenario #5: I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.		
Scenario #6: I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.		
Scenario #7: I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.		
Scenario #8: I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.		
Scenario #9: I avoid purchasing useless products.		
Scenario #10: I support forestation/Earth Hour.		
Scenario #11: I recycle papers and other scraps.		
Scenario #12: I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.		
Scenario #13: I do not throw trash anywhere.		
Scenario #14: I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.		
Scenario #15: When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.		
Scenario #16: I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty,		

staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.		
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Legend:

4:20-5.00 – very high adherence (VHA)

2.60-3.39- moderate adherence (MA)

1.00-1.79- no adherence (NA)

3.40-4.19- high adherence (HA)

1.80-2.59- low adherence (LA)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profiles of Respondents

The online survey that was made by the researchers collected data from the respondents to know their demographics. For the reason that some data that was collected were sensitive, the researchers redacted them after tabulating all of the said data in accordance to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, in which the researchers state that only those involved in the current study will have access to their given information and the exchange of which will be facilitated through email or hard copy. The researchers noticed that the most of the chosen respondents are in the age range of 17 - 20 years old, with 190 respondents, and 14 - 17 years old, with 92. Fascinatingly, a small number of people who answered in the survey are in the age range of 38 - 62 with a sum of 24 respondents overall, in which more females answered in the online survey, with 59.5% of the total number of respondents. Male respondents are tallied to be at 39.5%, while some respondents who do prefer not to say their gender is 1.0%. The living status of the respondents discloses that 37.4% of the respondents live with their relatives in the city, while 32.2% of them rent in the city. 29.4% are home owners while only 1.0% of the respondents are living under lease. As the most dominant age range of respondents is at 17 - 20 years old and 14 - 17 years old, it is usual to see that 80.8% of the respondents are still studying. 13.0% of them are employed, while 1.6% of them are self-employed. 0.5% of the respondents are business owners / co-owners while 3.9% of them are unemployed during the time of the survey. For the education status, the researchers saw that 0.8% are still on the elementary level and 1.6% have only an

elementary degree. 50.6% of the respondents were still in high school while 23.1% only had a high school degree, the college undergraduates that answered in the survey is 11.2%, while 10.4% of them finished a college degree. A marginal sector of respondents is studying in graduate school or have a Ph. D. or graduate degree.

General Concepts and Awareness of Carbon Footprint of the Respondents

The second part of the online survey organized by the researchers encompasses questions that tackle on the general concepts of carbon footprint as well as knowing how many people are aware of carbon footprints. After the culmination of the online survey that was conducted from January 14, 2021 to January 23, 2021, the researchers found out that 22.1% of the respondents do not know what is a carbon footprint and 19.7% also do not know that everyday habits may affect to the environment's carbon footprint. 87.5% of the respondents did not try to measure their carbon emissions before, despite the fact the fact that 77.9% of them know what is a carbon footprint. The respondents answered on to the question on if they agree that the effects of carbon footprints will disappear gave separate opinions as 15.6% agreed, 38.7% disagreed, and 45.7% are neutral to the question. However, 90.9% of the respondents agreed that the pandemic affected the amount the country's carbon emissions over the past few months. 57.9% of the respondents reminisced one activity that may aid in declining their carbon emissions while 42.1% did not. This is in stark contrast with the 67.3% of the respondents that have remembered to do something that may help reduce their carbon emissions. 52.2% of the respondents do not remember if they helped others to reduce their carbon emissions before the pandemic while 60.8% can recall one thing that they planned to do to lower their own emissions even during the pandemic.

Respondents by the numbers

Did not state barangay
0.3%

Figure 4.1: Tally of the number of Quezon City residents and the districts where they live along with respondents who live in places outside the city, marked as false positives.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Respondents

Demographics

Figure 4.2: Graphical representation of the Gender, Education Status, and Age Range of the chosen respondents for the online survey that was conducted by the researchers.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Respondents

Demographics

Figure 4.3: Graphical representation of the Marital Status, Living Status, and Employment Status of the chosen respondents for the online survey that was conducted by the researchers.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Responses

Survey Questions (Preliminary)

LEGEND

- Yes/Agree
- No/Disagree
- Neutral

QUESTIONS

1. Are you familiar with the phrase “carbon footprint”?
2. Are you aware that our everyday habits have a huge effect on adding to the environment’s carbon footprint?
3. Have you ever tried measuring your overall carbon emissions before?
4. Do you agree that the effects of carbon footprint will eventually disappear?
5. Do you think that the lockdown cause by COVID-19 affected our country’s total carbon emissions these past few months?
6. Can you recall one thing you did that you think helped reduce your carbon footprint before the pandemic started?
7. Can you recall one thing you did that you think helped reduce your carbon footprint DURING the pandemic?
8. Can you recall one thing you did that you think helped reduce the carbon footprint of others BEFORE the pandemic?
9. Can you recall one thing you planned to do to help reduce your carbon footprint even during the pandemic?

ANSWERS

Figure 4.4: Graphical representation of the nine survey questions on the second section of the online survey that was conducted by the researchers.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Measures and Extent of Adherence of Carbon Footprint of the Respondents

The third and fourth sections of the online survey prearranged by the researchers incorporates questions that tackle on the measures to diminish carbon footprint of the chosen respondents in their households or family circles and assessing the levels of adherence by which they follow the said measures. The said sections are patterned to a five-point Likert Scale Test that was from a study from a study made by Adanza in 2016 entitled, "Barriers to Mitigate Carbon Footprint in a Selected Academic Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines". At the end of the online survey the researchers noticed that the respondents of the survey put measures in reducing their footprints in a responsible manner, which ended up in the survey to have positive results with only quantitative indexes of VHA (very high adherence) and HA (high adherence) are present. though the researchers speculated that of them may have been well aware of their carbon footprint during the time of the pandemic. Table 4.1 displays the extent of level of adherence taken in reducing carbon footprint before the quarantine measures that was brought up by the COVID-19 pandemic, where only the scenarios #2, #3, #4, #5, #6, #8, #9, and #12 have a quantitative index of HA (high adherence). This can be compared to Table 4.2 which shows the extent of level of adherence taken in reducing carbon footprint during the quarantine that was brought up by the COVID-19 pandemic by which the scenarios #2, #3, #6, and #12 are the only ones left with HA.

Table 4.1: Extent of Level of Adherence taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint (Before the Quarantine Measures brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic)

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint (Before the Pandemic)	Mean (Margin of Error = $\pm 5\%$)	Quantitative Index (QI)
Scenario #1: I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.	4.63	VHA
Scenario #2: I change incandescent lamp or fluorescent to save more energy.	4.02	HA
Scenario #3: I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.	3.89	HA

Scenario #4: I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.	4.15	HA
Scenario #5: I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.	4.10	HA
Scenario #6: I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.	3.88	HA
Scenario #7: I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.	4.26	VHA
Scenario #8: I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.	4.17	HA
Scenario #9: I avoid purchasing useless products.	3.88	HA
Scenario #10: I support forestation/Earth Hour.	4.43	VHA
Scenario #11: I recycle papers and other scraps.	4.27	VHA
Scenario #12: I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.	3.83	HA
Scenario #13: I do not throw trash anywhere.	4.56	VHA
Scenario #14: I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.	4.28	VHA
Scenario #15: When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.	4.28	VHA
Scenario #16: I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty, staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.	4.11	VHA

Legend:

4.20-5.00 – very high adherence (VHA)

2.60-3.39- moderate adherence (MA)

1.00-1.79- no adherence (NA)

3.40-4.19- high adherence (HA)

1.80-2.59- low adherence (LA)

Table 4.2: Extent of Level of Adherence taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint
(During the Quarantine Measures brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic)

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint (During the Pandemic)	Mean (Margin of Error = $\pm 5\%$)	Quantitative Index (QI)
Scenario #1: I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.	4.73	VHA
Scenario #2: I change incandescent lamp or fluorescent to save more energy.	3.86	HA
Scenario #3: I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.	4.09	HA
Scenario #4: I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.	4.27	VHA
Scenario #5: I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.	4.21	VHA
Scenario #6: I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.	4.11	HA
Scenario #7: I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.	4.50	VHA
Scenario #8: I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.	4.41	VHA
Scenario #9: I avoid purchasing useless products.	4.37	VHA
Scenario #10: I support forestation/Earth Hour.	4.53	VHA
Scenario #11: I recycle papers and other scraps.	4.45	VHA
Scenario #12: I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.	4.09	HA
Scenario #13: I do not throw trash anywhere.	4.69	VHA
Scenario #14: I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.	4.52	VHA

Scenario #15: When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.	4.34	VHA
Scenario #16: I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty, staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.	4.29	VHA

Legend:

4:20-5.00 – very high adherence (VHA)

2.60-3.39- moderate adherence (MA)

1.00-1.79- no adherence (NA)

3.40-4.19- high adherence (HA)

1.80-2.59- low adherence (LA)

False Positives

The researchers observed that during the data collection of the respondents' answer, some people who aren't currently residing in Quezon City. The researchers conjectured that the problem with the said false positives is due to the massive area that the city has and some parts of the city is facing head-to-head to other provinces in Region IV – A (CALABARZON) and other cities in the National Capital Region (NCR). Another inference from the researchers is that a false positive may also come from a repeated entry of a person. The researchers captured two that live in Bulacan, four in Rizal, one from Makati, three from the city of San Juan, one from Malabon, and a repeated entry from someone who lives in Quezon City.

Responses

5-Point Likert Scale

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint Before the Quarantine

LEGEND

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

MEASURES

1. I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.
2. I change incandescent lamp to fluorescent to save more energy.
3. I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.
4. I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.
5. I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.
6. I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.
7. I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.
8. I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.

MORE...

INTENSITY

Figure 4.5: Graphical representation of the responses of the respondents on their action taken in reducing carbon footprint before the quarantine.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Responses

5-Point Likert Scale

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint
Before the Quarantine

LEGEND

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

MEASURES

9. I avoid purchasing useless products.
10. I support forestation/Earth Hour.
11. I recycle papers and other scraps.
12. I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.
13. I do not throw trash anywhere.
14. I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.
15. When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.
16. I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty, staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.

INTENSITY

Figure 4.5 (continued): Graphical representation of the responses of the respondents on their action taken in reducing carbon footprint before the quarantine.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Responses

5-Point Likert Scale

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint During the Quarantine

LEGEND

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

MEASURES

1. I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.
2. I change incandescent lamp to fluorescent to save more energy.
3. I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not.
4. I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.
5. I minimize use of warm water in taking shower.
6. I prefer to buy local products rather than imported ones.
7. I use reusable cloth tote-style bag rather than plastic bags.
8. I prefer to select energy-efficient one when purchasing appliances, gadgets that require or use energy.

MORE...

INTENSITY

Figure 4.6: Graphical representation of the responses of the respondents on their action taken in reducing carbon footprint during the quarantine.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

Responses

5-Point Likert Scale

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint During the Quarantine

MEASURES

- 9. I avoid purchasing useless products.
- 10. I support forestation/Earth Hour.
- 11. I recycle papers and other scraps.
- 12. I practice decomposing biodegradable wastes.
- 13. I do not throw trash anywhere.
- 14. I do not buy excess food to avoid throwing away food or extra condiments.
- 15. When throwing garbage, I segregate waste and dispose it properly.
- 16. I encourage my fellow classmates, students, faculty, staff/administrators to re-use papers or spoilage when printing.

LEGEND

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

INTENSITY

Figure 4.6 (continued): Graphical representation of the responses of the respondents on their action taken in reducing carbon footprint during the quarantine.

Figure by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers noticed that on Table 4.1, the extent of level of adherence taken in reducing carbon footprint before the quarantine measures have the scenarios #2, #3, #4, #5, #6, #8, #9, and #12 have a quantitative index of HA (high adherence). This is emphasizing that household appliances do produce large amounts of carbon footprint into the environment. Comparing it to Table 4.2, which shows the extent of level of adherence taken in reducing carbon footprint during the quarantine where the scenarios #2, #3, #6, and #12 are the only ones left with HA, the researchers concluded that there is very high adherence among the residents of Quezon City in their measures to reduce their carbon footprint, however there are still ways to go to change the level of adherence for scenarios that are related to saving energy in homes, especially on using appliances and managing excessive habits. In addition to this, the researchers realized that the city residents maintain a very high adherence of reducing their carbon footprint, which can be conjectured by the education status of the residents who joined the survey by which most of them are studying.

The researchers would like to recommend that there might be problems in regards to the collection of data in the used medium (Google Forms) and similar other platforms while conducting an online survey (Microsoft Forms, Typeform, JotForm, etc.) in a densely populated urban area such as Quezon City. The researchers noticed that most of the respondents answering the said survey may be connected to the internet using mobile data connections, some respondents may also leave out an incomplete address to the survey, leaving out a familiar area in their place instead of the complete address. Another recommendation would be that many of the older respondents in this survey may need assistance in utilizing the platform used in the survey (Google Forms) as they might not have been familiar with the usage of it. For some extent, the utilization of online surveys in doing quantitative studies like these can be a barrier to know the measures of adherence of people, not only in rural areas but also in urban areas also.

The local government, and specifically to the government of Quezon City, must also enhance their enforcement of green management in the city as well as to promote and maintain advocacies in the city to mitigate carbon footprint. This must also be done

in each barangay in order to reinforce environmental awareness. The public academic institutions in the city must also be a part of strengthening the cause of this movement in order to teach students about being a part of environmental conservation and the importance of carbon footprint advocacy.

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PHOTO CREDITS

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: TABLES AND GRAPHS

Appendix A1 – A4 – The screenshots of the tables and graphs of the online survey and the five-point Likert Scale Test made by the researchers that was tabulated via Google Sheets.

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

APPENDIX B: SURVEY FORM

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quez

Questions Responses

Section 1 of 6

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols

Survey Disclaimer:

The collected personal information will be utilized solely by the proponents for documentation, statistical reports, and processing purposes within the study entitled, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols" and will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Only those involved in the study will have access to this personal information, the exchange of which will be facilitated through email or hard copy. The data will be kept in spreadsheet format under the secured storage of Google Forms, Google Slides, and the local computer drives of the authorized

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quez

Questions Responses

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 6

Survey Questions

DIRECTIONS: The following are the survey questions for our study, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols". Read each statement carefully and choose the response option on the right based on what you feel at the moment. There is no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement, but give the answer which seems to describe your present feelings best.

The researchers hope for a honest response from you, dear respondent. Feel free to take your time in answering these questions.

Are you familiar with the phrase "carbon footprint"? *

Yes

No

Are you aware that our everyday habits have a huge effect on adding to the environment's carbon footprint? *

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quez

Section 3 of 6

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint Before the Quarantine

DIRECTIONS: Read each statement below and choose the response option on the right based on your experiences BEFORE the occurrence of quarantine due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Please be honest as much as possible and remember that there is no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement, but give the answer which seems to describe your present feelings best.

The Likert Scale Test for this survey is adapted from the study by Adanza (2016) entitled "Barriers to Mitigate Carbon Footprint in a Selected Academic Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines".

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint *

This is a Likert Scale Test and the choices available are strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. Please be guided to choose the best option applicable to your lifestyle BEFORE the quarantine period.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagr...
I turn off applia...	<input type="radio"/>				
I change incand...	<input type="radio"/>				
I wash clothes ...	<input type="radio"/>				
I use bicycle or ...	<input type="radio"/>				

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quez

Section 4 of 6

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint During the Quarantine

DIRECTIONS: Read each statement below and choose the response option on the right based on your experiences DURING quarantine period due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Please be honest as much as possible and remember that there is no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement, but give the answer which seems to describe your present feelings best.

The Likert Scale Test for this survey is adapted from the study by Adanza (2016) entitled "Barriers to Mitigate Carbon Footprint in a Selected Academic Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines".

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint *

This is a Likert Scale Test and the choices available are strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. Please be guided to choose the best option applicable to your lifestyle DURING the quarantine period.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagr...
I turn off applia...	<input type="radio"/>				
I change incand...	<input type="radio"/>				
I wash clothes ...	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix B1 – B4 – The screenshots of the online survey and the five-point Likert Scale Test made by the researchers.

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Appendix B5 – B6 – The screenshots of the consent and authorization verification made by the researchers. (Appendix B6 shows the responses tab where the form is not accepting responses.)

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols

Survey Disclaimer:

The collected personal information will be utilized solely by the proponents for documentation, statistical reports, and processing purposes within the study entitled, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols" and will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Only those involved in the study will have access to this personal information, the exchange of which will be facilitated through email or hard copy. The data will be kept in spreadsheet format under the secured storage of Google Forms, Google Slides, and the local computer drives of the authorized personnel. The compiled data will be used as reference information for the undergoing research study. You have the right to edit your submission in this survey as long as it will not tamper with our data during the time period of this study. You have also the right to ask for a copy of any personal information we hold about you, as well as to ask for it to be corrected. To do so,

Survey Questions

DIRECTIONS: The following are the survey questions for our study, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols". Read each statement carefully and choose the response option on the right based on what you feel at the moment. There is no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement, but give the answer which seems to describe your present feelings best.

The researchers hope for a honest response from you, dear respondent. Feel free to take your time in answering these questions.

Are you familiar with the phrase "carbon footprint"? *

- Yes
- No

Are you aware that our everyday habits have a huge effect on adding to the environment's carbon footprint? *

- Yes
- No

Have you ever tried measuring your overall carbon emissions before? *

- Yes
- No

Appendix B7 – B8 – The screenshots of the first sections where the respondent answers to the prepared online survey on Google Forms by the researchers.

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint Before the Quarantine

DIRECTIONS: Read each statement below and choose the response option on the right based on your experiences BEFORE the occurrence of quarantine due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Please be honest as much as possible and remember that there is no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement, but give the answer which seems to describe your present feelings best.

The Likert Scale Test for this survey is adapted from the study by Adanza (2016) entitled "Barriers to Mitigate Carbon Footprint in a Selected Academic Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines".

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint *

This is a Likert Scale Test and the choices available are strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. Please be guided to choose the best option applicable to your lifestyle BEFORE the quarantine period.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.	<input type="radio"/>				
I change incandescent lamp to fluorescent to save more energy.	<input type="radio"/>				
I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not	<input type="radio"/>				
I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.	<input type="radio"/>				

Actions taken in Reducing Carbon Footprint During the Quarantine

DIRECTIONS: Read each statement below and choose the response option on the right based on your experiences DURING quarantine period due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Please be honest as much as possible and remember that there is no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement, but give the answer which seems to describe your present feelings best.

The Likert Scale Test for this survey is adapted from the study by Adanza (2016) entitled "Barriers to Mitigate Carbon Footprint in a Selected Academic Institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines".

Measures to Reduce Carbon Footprint *

This is a Likert Scale Test and the choices available are strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. Please be guided to choose the best option applicable to your lifestyle DURING the quarantine period.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I turn off appliances, lights or other gadgets when not in use.	<input type="radio"/>				
I change incandescent lamp to fluorescent to save more energy.	<input type="radio"/>				
I wash clothes alternatively if clothes to be washed are not	<input type="radio"/>				
I use bicycle or just walk for short journey.	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix B9 – B10 – The screenshots of the sections where the five-point Likert Scale Test on the actions taken before and during the quarantine where the respondent answers to the prepared online survey on Google Forms by the researchers. (Appendix B9 – Actions before the quarantine; Appendix B10 – Actions during the quarantine.)

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Consent and Authorization Verification

This section of this survey is for verifying your consent on the responses that you have submitted for our study, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols".

I, the undersigned, hereby expressly agree, consent, and authorize the proponents of this study to collect and process the following personal information related to me:

1. Email Address
2. Full Name
3. Age
4. Gender
5. Complete Address
6. Contact Number
7. Living Status
8. Marital Status
9. Education Status
10. Employment Status

I agree that the above-mentioned personal information shall be processed for the following purposes:

1. Generate Directory of Survey Participants
2. Documents for Scientific Publications / Research Reports

I agree that the above-mentioned personal information shall be processed in the following manner:

1. Storage in a Data Base
2. Storage in Computer Files
3. Storage on Cloud Computer Files (Google Drive)

I agree that the above-mentioned personal information may be disclosed to the following recipients for the following purposes:

1. Survey Participant (Recipient)

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols

Online Survey Response: Submitted

Thank you for taking your time to respond to this online survey, dear respondent. Your answers will be confidential and will be used only for academic purposes.

Mag-e-email ng kopya ng iyong mga tugon sa address na ibinigay mo.

Huwag isumite kailanman ang mga password sa pamamagitan ng Google Forms.

Appendix B11 – B12 – The screenshots of the last sections where the respondent reads and answers the consent and verification form for the survey made by the researchers.

Screenshots taken by: *Marc Andrie M. Bermundo*

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronav... .XLSX ☆ t Share

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	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB
1	Likert Scale Measure #1	Likert Scale Measure #2	Likert Scale Measure #3	Likert Scale Measure #4	Likert Scale Measure #5	Likert Scale Measure #6	Likert Scale Measure #7
2	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree
3	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
4	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree
5	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
6	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
7	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
8	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree				
9	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
10	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
11	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
12	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
13	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
14	Agree						
15	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Agree
16	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
17	Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
18	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
19	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
20	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
21	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
22	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
23	Strongly Agree						
24	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
25	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
26	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
27	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

Form Responses 1 Explore

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	AL	AM	AN	AO	AP	AQ	AR
1	Likert Scale Measure #1	Likert Scale Measure #2	Likert Scale Measure #3	Likert Scale Measure #4	Likert Scale Measure #5	Likert Scale Measure #6	Likert Scale Measure #7
2	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
3	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Agree
4	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
5	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
6	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
7	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
8	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree				
9	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
10	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
11	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
12	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree				
13	Strongly Agree						
14	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
15	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree
16	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
17	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
18	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
19	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
20	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
21	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
22	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
23	Strongly Agree						
24	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
25	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
26	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
27	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

Form Responses 1 Explore

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronav... .XLSX ☆ t Share

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	AW	AX	AY	AZ	BA	BB	BC
1	Likert Scale Measure #12	Likert Scale Measure #13	Likert Scale Measure #14	Likert Scale Measure #15	Likert Scale Measure #16	Online Survey Validation	
2	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Submit	
3	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Submit	
4	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Submit	
5	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Submit	
6	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Submit	
7	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Submit	
8	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Submit	
9	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Submit	
10	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Submit	
11	Strongly Agree	Submit					
12	Strongly Agree	Submit					
13	Strongly Agree	Submit					
14	Strongly Agree	Submit					
15	Strongly Agree	Submit					
16	Strongly Agree	Submit					
17	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Submit	
18	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Submit	
19	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Submit	
20	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Submit	
21	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Submit	
22	Undecided	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Submit	
23	Strongly Agree	Submit					
24	Strongly Agree	Submit					
25	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Submit	
26	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Submit	
27	Strongly Agree	Submit					

Form Responses 1 Explore

Appendix C1 – C5 – The screenshots of the list of online survey responses in spreadsheet format, by which the sensitive data that the researchers collected is redacted for their privacy.

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

Online Survey: Evaluation on the Re ... Protocols (Redacted Responses).pdf Open with Google Docs

Timestamp	E-mail Address	Full Name (Last Name, First Name, M.I.)
1/14/2021 12:07:45	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 12:13:36	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 12:46:34	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 12:46:31	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 13:16:37	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 14:02:56	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 15:24:46	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 16:37:49	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 18:55:34	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 19:20:34	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 20:19:25	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 20:50:15	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 21:07:05	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 22:23:50	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 22:58:08	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/14/2021 23:11:26	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 1:10:58	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 3:10:36	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 3:32:10	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 3:34:09	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 3:34:15	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 3:45:17	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 5:22:45	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 5:36:25	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 5:50:22	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 5:58:31	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 7:39:30	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 8:29:22	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 9:15:18	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 9:23:27	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 10:08:04	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 10:22:59	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 10:50:56	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 11:03:56	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 11:46:12	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 12:18:22	REDACTED	REDACTED
1/15/2021 12:25:13	REDACTED	REDACTED

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Online Survey: Evaluation on the Re... Protocols (Redacted Responses).pdf

Open with Google Docs

Yes		Yes
Yes		Yes
No		No
Yes		Yes
No		No
No		No
Yes		Yes
No		Yes
Yes		No
Yes		Yes
Yes		Yes
No		Yes
No		No
No		No

Likert Scale Measure #1	Likert Scale Measure #2	Likert Scale Measure #3	Likert Scale Measure #4
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided

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Drive

Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

Likert Scale Measure #5	Likert Scale Measure #6	Likert Scale Measure #7	Likert Scale Measure #8
Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Disagree	Agree	Undecided
Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree

Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree

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Appendix C6 – C8 – The screenshots of the list of online survey responses, presented in portable document file (PDF) format, by which the sensitive data that the researchers collected is redacted for their privacy.

Screenshots taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo

APPENDIX D: INVITATIONS TO THE ONLINE SURVEY

Appendix D1 – An invitation the survey that was posted by Mark Jonel V. Abad on the social media platform, Facebook last January 15, 2021. The caption of the post contains the request to collect data for this study and the prompts by the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The picture inside the post is the first PowerPoint slide used in the project defense of the study.

Screenshot taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo.

Facebook Link: <https://www.facebook.com/AbadAbadAbad.23/posts/1356425464700131>

Caption:

Good day! We, senior high school researchers of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, would want to collect data for our study entitled, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols".

Survey link: <https://forms.gle/T291QJhTm26c2hEr9>

The data to be collected in this survey will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. We are hoping for a complete and honest response. Thank you.

Appendix D2 – The invitation for the survey that was originally posted by Mark Jonel V. Abad on Facebook was then shared by Marc Andrie M. Bermundo on the following day. The caption of the post also contains the request to collect data for this study and the reminders brought by the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Screenshot taken by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo.

Facebook Link: <https://www.facebook.com/xbloodyxscythex/posts/1653313208206090>

Caption:

(Reposting this as we need more survey participants.)

Greetings! The researchers of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School are requesting for participants for their study entitled, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols".

This survey is available to those living within Quezon City and is open for all ages.

To proceed with this online survey, click or tap the link: <https://forms.gle/T291QJhTm26c2hEr9>

The data to be collected in this survey will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. We are hoping for a complete and honest response. Thank you.

Appendix D3 – These are the invitation message that the researchers have spread through Facebook Messenger, in which the participants can enter to the survey generated using Google Forms.

Message Version 1:

Good day! The senior high school researchers of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School would want to collect data for their study entitled, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols". The data that will be collected in this survey will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researchers are hoping for a complete and honest response. Thank you.

Link: <https://forms.gle/T291QJhTm26c2hEr9>

Message Version 2:

Greetings! The researchers of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School are requesting for participants for their study entitled, "Evaluation on the Reduction of Carbon Footprints of Quezon City Residents under the Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Quarantine Protocols".

This survey is available to those living within Quezon City and is open for all ages.

To proceed with this online survey, click or tap the link: <https://forms.gle/T291QJhTm26c2hEr9>

The data to be collected in this survey will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. We are hoping for a complete and honest response. Thank you.